

A

DISSERTATION

ON

A RELATIONSHIP STUDY ON SUICIDAL TENDENCY AND
DEPRESSION AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

Abstract

This study is investigated depression and suicidal ideation among college students. The students in this study were between 18 and 22 years old, numbering 100 in total. The number of male students was 50, while female students were 50. A correlational study will be carry out in the study. The study adopted a descriptive research design, and purposive sampling technique was used to select the population. Data was analyzed using mean, standard deviation and Pearson product Moment correlation.

In this study, the forefront will be on people who were depressed and more prone to suicidal ideation, when someone who

is experiencing family issues, violence, abuse, anxiety disorder and behaviour problem will be the focal point. One of the recommendations in the study is that mental health professional need to address and make better policies to understand the need of training in identifying and counselling the students to prevent suicide among college students and mental health issues and suicidality affecting students in tertiary institutions.

Suicidal Tendency, Suicidal Behaviour, Suicidal ideation, depression, Suicide usually results from the interaction of many factors, depression being the most common and significant but not the only risk factor for suicide.

✓ **Keywords**

Suicidal Tendency, Suicidal Behaviour, Suicidal ideation, Suicidal thoughts, suicide, depression, mental health, college stress, perceived stress, college students, female college students, male college students, lucknow, relationship study, mental disorders, family issues, violence, abuse and behaviour problem .

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Chapter 1 : Introduction

Suicide is the second leading cause of death in college students, making it a significant public health concern on college campuses. Perceived stress, depression, and mental health stigma are established risk factors for engaging in suicidal behaviors; however, their interrelationships are unknown.

In a sample, 100 college students, we examined the role of suicidal behaviour as a potential mediator of the relation between suicidal tendency and depression, as a moderator of that effect.

Additionally, depressive symptoms partially mediated the relation between depression and suicidal behaviors, such that greater suicidal behaviour was related to more depression and, in turn, to greater engagement in suicidal behavior.

Negative, unaccepting attitudes toward mental health treatment, such as fear of social repercussion, may contribute to a worsening of symptoms and suicide risk in students experiencing distress. Our Findings may have clinical and public health implications. At the individual level, addressing stress and depression, perhaps by bolstering coping efficacy via Cognitive Behavioral Therapy and, at the community level, implementing strategies to reduce

mental health stigma, perhaps via Awareness messaging campaigns, may reduce risk for suicide.

Suicide is the deliberate act of killing oneself. Suicide is most commonly committed due to depression and a sense of injustice. The pressure from parents to perform well in national board examinations, particularly for Class XII, before graduating school is a prevalent reason of anxiety in adolescent suicide.

A suicidal individual may not ask for assistance, begins with recognizing and taking warning signs carefully. If you suspect a friend or family member is contemplating suicide, you may be hesitant to bring it up. However, honestly discussing suicide thoughts and sentiments can save a life. Despite its tragic nature, death by suicide is a relatively rare phenomenon, and it is much more likely that suicide reduction efforts will have an impact on the amelioration of suicidal behaviors. Suicidal behaviors are comprised of "behaviors that don't always result in death, but are "related" to the process or concept of self-inflicted death" (Silverman, Berman, Sanddal, O'Carroll, & Joiner, 2007b, p. 272).

Suicidal behaviors are one of the communicative aspects of suicide, which includes thoughts about suicide, or ideation, and suicide attempts, as

well as the severity and frequency of these behaviors (Silverman et al., 2007a; Silverman et. Al., 2007b). given the high rates of suicidal behavior and death by suicide in young adults, it is important to identify factors that may play a role in such poor outcomes.

Indeed, the success of prevention and intervention strategies is predicated on the identification of risk and protective factors that influence the likelihood of engaging in suicidal behavior (Webb, Hirsch, & Toussaint, 2015).

Wasserman and Wasserman (2010) defined suicidal ideation as thinking about and engaging in it, writing, talking or planning it. Johal and Sharma (2016) proposed that suicidal ideation refers to a scale of thoughts ranging from mild to severe about death, which include thoughts and feelings about death, hurting them self, or even to the "planning, conduct and result" of own suicide. Suicidal ideation alone may lead to serious suicidal behaviors.

According to Menezes et al (2012), 10.7% and 18.4% of 206 undergraduate had suicidal ideation while only 1.0% of respondents had a suicide plan or a suicide attempt due to dissatisfaction with academic performance, being in the clinical semesters, having history of drug abuse and feeling neglected by parents.

Depression was the second strongest predictor for suicide in the past study by Tin et al (2014). Shamsuddin, Fadzil, Ismail, Shah, Omar and Muhammad (2013) reported the level of depression among Malaysian university students at moderate, severe and extremely severe depression were 27.5%, 9.7% and 9.7 respectively.

Various factor that may contribute to depression which includes (and not limited to) poor academic performance, life satisfaction, social support, life stressor, physical inactivity, overweight or obesity, and sleeping problems. Past studies focused on gender differences in depression and revealed that females have higher depression compared to male.

Armstrong and Oomen-Early (2009) found that female college students had higher depression than male students. Islam et al (2016) stated that female students more depressed than male students due to academic stress and future careers. However, Kok and Goh (2011) view of point said that suicidal ideation is higher in males as compared to females due to love relationships.

There was also another study stated that there was no difference in depression between both genders where it shows a low level of depression among university students (Sarokhani et al., 2013; Mustaffa et al., 2013).

Ram Et al (2018) also stated that suicidal ideation was more prevalence among females as compared to male students. Study by Osama et al (2014) supports this statement where females' students have a higher prevalence of suicidal ideation than males' students. However, Panda (2015) found that there were no significant differences between male and female students on suicidal ideation.

Thus, this study aimed to measure the relationship between depression and suicidal ideation among college students in Lucknow. Besides, to the extent of researchers' knowledge, to this current date there was lack of study done on determining the relationship of depression and suicidal ideation among college students, specifically in Lucknow .

On college campuses, depression and other mental health disorders are a substantial public health issue. Many college students have their first psychiatric episode, and 12 to 18% of students have a diagnosable mental disease (Mowbray, Megiven, & Mandiberg, 2006). According to Epidemiological Studies, the 15 to 21 age group (Typical College Years) has the greatest past-year prevalence rate of mental illness at 39%. According to Eisenberg (2007), the overall prevalence of depression and degree is 16% among undergraduate students and 13% among graduate students. According to the results of the

American College Health Association's (Acha) National College Health Assessment (NCHA), the percentage of students who have been Diagnosed with Depression has Climbed From 10% in 2000 to 18% in 2008 (2000, 2008).

A variety of factors contribute to the onset of depression through college. Young adults face additional life pressures as they explore their identity, struggle to acquire new abilities, are away from established social support systems, and have increased time demands as they transition from home to college (Dyson & Renk, 2006).

Suicide warning signs include:

- **Talking about suicide**:- Any talk about suicide, dying, or self-harm, such as "I wish I hadn't been born," "If I see you again..." and "I'd be better off dead."
- **Seeking out lethal means**:- Seeking access to guns, pills, knives, or other objects that could be used in a suicide attempt.
- **Preoccupation with death**:- Unusual focus on death, dying, or violence. Writing poems or stories about death.
- **No hope for the future**:- Feelings of helplessness, hopelessness, and being trapped ("There's no way out"). Belief that things will never get better or change.

- **Self-loathing, self-hatred**:- Feelings of worthlessness, guilt, shame, and self-hatred. Feeling like a burden ("Everyone would be better off without me")
- **Getting affairs in order**:- Making out a will. Giving away prized possessions. Making arrangements for family members.
- **Saying goodbye**:- Unusual or unexpected visits or calls to family and friends. Saying goodbye to people as if they won't be seen again.
- **Withdrawing from others**:- Withdrawing from friends and family. Increasing social isolation. Desire to be left alone.
- **Self-destructive behavior**:- Increased alcohol or drug use, reckless driving, unsafe sex. Taking unnecessary risks as if they have a "death wish."
- **Sudden sense of calm**:- A sudden sense of calm and happiness after being extremely depressed can mean that the person has made a decision to attempt suicide.

Cause of College students suicide

Suicidal ideation can occur when a person feels they are no longer able to cope with an overwhelming situation. This could stem from financial problems, death of a loved one, a broken relationship, or a devastating or debilitating illness. The most common situations or life events that might cause suicidal thoughts are grief, sexual abuse, financial problems,

remorse, rejection, a relationship breakup, and unemployment. Different kinds of troubling and difficult situations can make a teen consider suicide. The same emotional states that make adults vulnerable to considering suicide also apply to adolescents.

Those with good support system (e.g., among family and peers, or extracurricular sport, social, or religious associations) are likely to have an outlet to help them deal with their feelings. Other without such networks are more susceptible during their emotional changes, and may feel that they are all alone in times of trouble. Everyone should have someone with whom they can share he or she sorrows and concerns. When a person does not share their thoughts and feelings with anyone and bottle up their feelings, they become a ticking atom bomb, which can and will burst any second. **People who are depressed mostly commit suicide.**

Depression is a mental health disorder. It causes chemical imbalance in the brain, which can lead to despondency, lethargy, or general apathy towards life. Depression is a common mental disorder which had become a powerful trigger of suicidal ideation. The aim is to identify the difference and relationship of depression and suicidal ideation among college students. Depression is a very crucial public health concern that often associated

with depressed mood, loss of concentration or desire, decreased energy, feelings of guilt or low self-esteem, wroubled in sleeping or hunger, and poor focus in doing something doing something (WHO, 2012).

Depression affects mental health problems between the young group mostly institution of higher learning students due to stress caused from studies and independent living (Islam et al., 2018). Zuo et al (2020) proposed that stressful life events have a direct and positive influence on depression. Depression usually linked with a decrease in the quality of life, increased morbidity and mortality. Furthermore, depressions also influence physical and psychological well-being as it is related to acute contagious diseases, suicidal thoughts, and suicide (Buchanan, 2012; Zuo et al., 2020).

Depression is a serious mental health problem that may lead to different ripple effects in students. One of such ripple effects is suicidal ideation or suicidal thoughts which may lead to suicide attempts or suicide. Suicidality or suicidal behaviour exists along a continuum that extends from suicidal ideation or thoughts, suicide related communications, suicide attempts and finally suicide (CDCP, 2008).

The following risk factors may have an impact on the probability of someone experiencing suicidal ideation:

- A family history of mental health issues
- A family history of substance abuse
- A family history of violence
- A family history of suicide
- A feeling of hopelessness
- A feeling of seclusion or loneliness
- Being under the influence of alcohol or drugs
- Having a problem with substance abuse
- Having a psychiatric disorder or mental illness
- Being prone to reckless or impulsive behavior

The most common diagnosis in college students who commit suicide is depression and usually found in those with suicidal ideations and suicide attempts. Depression is attached with anxiety, high levels of stress, and in the worst possible cases with suicide. It can also affect one's personal life, school life, work life, social life and family life. This can further lead to isolation from friends, family and society that may create other

problems. It is a real severe condition that can affect a person's all the aspects of his life and need urgent medication.

Depression varies from person to person, but there are some common signs and symptoms. Common symptoms of depression in college students are:

Depression or irritable mood

- Temper, agitation
- Loss of interest in activities, apathy
- Reduced pleasure in daily activities
- Loss or increase of appetite or a significant
- Persistent difficulty falling asleep or staying asleep
- Excessive daytime sleepiness
- Fatigue
- Difficultly concentrating
- Difficultly making decisions
- Memory loss (amnesia) episodes
- Preoccupation with self
- Feeling of worthlessness, sadness, or self-hatred
- Excessive or inappropriate feelings of guilt

- Acting-out behaviour (missing curfews, unusual defiance)
- Thoughts about suicide or obsessive fears or worries about death
- Giving actual suicide attempt or plan to do so

If there symptoms persist for at least two weeks and cause significant distress or difficulty functioning, treatment should be sought.

Depression and suicidal ideation are serious mental conditions that put those affected at risk for attempted suicide or suicide. The developed world, unlike developing countries has carried out a number of researches that have linked depression and suicidality in students.

Such researches have provided the developed world with statistical data that can be used to provide assistance to those who are prone to depression and suicidality.

Background

Lucknow is not known to have a data bank where information on depression and suicidality among students with and without learning disabilities can be accessed. Lack of information on depression and suicidality in college students is due to grief, sexual abuse, financial

problems, remorse, rejection, a relationship breakup, and unemployment. Research on depression and suicidality in lucknow will provide statistics that can guide mental health experts and related professionals on how to overcome these problems. Students, with or without suicidal behaviors , need to be assisted to overcome factors that predispose them to depression and suicidal ideation so that they will not go on to attempt or commit suicide.

College is a difficult setting for most young people, it is especially crucial for parents, friends, instructors, and counselors to intervene if they Suspect a student is depressed students are usually hesitant to seek therapy because of societal stigmas associated with depression. Before developing a treatment plan, at risk adolescents should undergo a mental health evaluation that includes their developmental and family history. School performance, and any self-injury behaviors.

The most effective treatments for depression in college-aged students are usually a mix of antidepressant medicines and talk therapies such as cognitive behavioral therapy and Interpersonal Psychotherapy.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The following research questions were formulated to guide the direction of the study.

- *There will be significant relationship between male and female college students with respect to depression.*
- *There will be significant between male and female college students with respect to suicidal behaviour.*
- *There will be significant relationship between suicidal behavior and Depression of male and female college students.*

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

- ❖ *To study the suicidal behaviour among male and female college students.*
- ❖ *To compare the male and female college students on depression level.*
- ❖ *To study the relationship between suicidal behavior and Depression among male and female college students.*

Chapter 2 : Review of literature

This Chapter presents the literature related to depression and suicidal ideation among students. This Section contains reviews of literature related to depression and suicidal ideation among students. It is helpful for the researcher to know about the tools and instruments which prove to be helpful and promising in the previous studies. The advantage of the related literature is also to provide insight into statistical methods through which validity of results is to be established. By reviewing the related literature the researcher can avoid unfruitful and useless problem areas.

Every research work is a step towards acquiring new knowledge and this knowledge is always based on previously gained knowledge. Hence, it should take into accounts, all the relevant information, thinking and researches that have provided it. A researcher ought to be well acquainted with the previous researchers related to his/her area of investigation. Review of literature help to develop the researcher, an insight of the problem to be investigated, to get information of what others have done in related field, and what remains to be done.

Welch (2019) found significant increases in major depression, serious psychological distress which includes anxiety and hopelessness and suicidal

thoughts and suicide attempts among teens and young adults with smaller, more inconsistent increases among adults age 26 and older in the researchers the rate of adolescents reporting symptoms consistent with major depression in the last 12 months rose from 8.7 percent in 2005 to 13.2 percent in 2017. In young adults age 18 to 25, it increased from 8.1 percent in 2009 to 13.2 percent in 2017.

Schlozman & Tedder (2019) explored that Depression and suicidal thoughts are two of the most frightening things a person can face in their lifetime. Depression has long been linked to suicidal thoughts and suicide attempts. Unfortunately, acting on those suicidal thoughts is a far too common scenario for many across the world, including students. In fact, suicide is the second-leading cause of death for those between the ages of 15 and 24. Depression is quite common in fact, between 30 and 70 percent of suicide victims suffer from major depression or a related disorder.

World Health Organization (2018) found that suicide is the second leading cause of death among 15-29-year-olds globally. Nearly 8,00,000 people die due to suicide every year, which is one person every 40 seconds. The prevention of suicide has not been adequately addressed due to a lack of

awareness of suicide as a major public health problem and the taboo in many societies to openly discuss it.

Till date, only a few countries have included suicide prevention among their health priorities and only 38 countries report having a national suicide prevention strategy. 79 per cent of suicides occurred in low and middle-income countries in 2016. Suicide accounted for 1.4 per cent of all deaths worldwide making it the 18th leading cause of death in 2016. Failure in examinations led to 2,413 suicides by students in 2016 or seven every day accounting for 25 per cent of student suicides. The National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) in its 2015 data made a shocking revelation that in India, one student commits suicide every hour.

Business standard (2018) assessed that 9,474 students committed suicide in 2016 almost 26 every day, according to a reply to the Lok Sabha by H G Ahir, Minister of State for Home Affairs, on January 2. Student suicides in the country have increased 52 per cent from 17 every day (6,248) in 2007 to 26 every day in 2016, data show Around 75,000 students committed suicides in India between 2007 and 2016. Maharashtra reported the most 1,350 student suicides in 2016, four every day, followed by West Bengal (1,147) and Tamil Nadu (981)

Amare, Woldeyhannes, Haile & Yeneabat (2018) revealed that prevalence and factors associated with suicide ideation and suicide attempt among adolescent high school students in Dangila Town, Ethiopia. The ages were 15- 19 years, respectively. The prevalence of suicide ideation and attempt was 22.5 percent and 16.2 percent respectively. School absenteeism and poor social support were positively associated with suicide ideation. Poor social support and being physically hurt were positively associated with suicide attempt. Unlike previous studies of adolescents in low-income countries, they find no association between gender or alcohol use and suicidal thoughts or attempts. They found that at least one in five of the adolescents experienced suicide ideation and one in six had attempted suicide

Pianowski, Fernandes & Baptista (2015) revealed a predominant female sample, in economically active ages and several levels of schooling. On the objectives, it was a prevalent approach in the construct and its relationship with other variables depression, chronic pain, hopelessness, ruminant and traumatic historical thinking, in addition to substance use, family and social support, socioeconomic status, sexuality and others.

Mehta, Pattanayak & Sagar (2015) reported the psychological health of adolescents can be affected by several family, school, peer and lifestyle-

related stressors. Mental and behavioral disorders including depression, anxiety, schizophrenia and substance use disorders are more prevalent in this age group. Indian youth may have of the highest suicide rates among younger populations across the world. Age and culture - sensitive interventions are needed to promote and protect the mental health of the adolescent population in India. In view of these unique psychological and psychiatric issues, the adolescent psychiatry merits a special emphasis.

Samuel (2013) reported that suicide and self-harm is an increasing global concern. Every year almost one million people die from suicide globally. It is among the three leading causes of death among those aged 15-44 years in some countries, and the second leading cause of death in the 10-24 years age group; these figures do not include suicide attempts which are up to 20 times more frequent than completed suicide. Suicide rates have been highest among in the male elderly however rate among young people have been increasing to the extent that they are now the highest in group in many countries both in the developed and developing countries.

Consoli, et. Al. (2013) assessed the link between family factors and suicidal behaviors, adjusting for several confounding factors, in a large community based sample of adolescents aged 17 years. The prevalence of

suicide differs substantially between boys and girls, the impact of familial risk factors would differ according to gender. It was also hypothesized that the role of current depression, family risk would be related to depression severity, defined as depression associated with suicidal ideation in the last year and or life time suicide attempt.

Sharma, Sharma & Yadava (2011) studied the relationship between parental styles and depression among adolescent. The result showed that Authoritarian Parenting style has significant positive correlation with depression, Permissive Parenting style has significant negative correlation with depression, There is a significant difference between males and females on measures of depression, The two extreme groups (high vs low) showed significant differences on their depression levels.

Chapter 3 : Rational of the Study

Significance of the Study

This study is important and needed for several reasons. There is a gap exist in the knowledge of factors leading to suicidal attempt among college students. The available literature focuses on the aspects of the suicidal attempt. Thus, the goal of this study is to focus on qualitative findings in order in order in gain in depth understanding of the factors leading to suicidal attempt among college students.

It is seen that there is increase in suicide rate in India and along with other age group it is increased in students also. This study will add new knowledge to this neglected area and also provide information to health care providers, educators, mental health professional and policy makers to better understand the need of training in identifying and counseling the students to prevent suicide among college students. Finally, this study will provide information for future researchers who wish to study the different aspects of suicide in different age group.

Chapter 4 : Methodology

The methodological procedures used in this study are introduced in this chapter. The topics are the . The method used for the selection of the participants and the characteristics of the sample are included in the first section. The Instruments used in the study are explained in the second section. The data collection procedure is clarified in the next chapter. The following chapter introduces the Statistical techniques for the analysis of the data. Finally, limitations of the study will be presented in following chapters.

Research Problem

The research problem for the present study will be **SUICIDAL TENDENCY AND DEPRESSION AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS.**

Objective of the Study

- ✓ To study the suicidal behaviour among male and female college students.
- ✓ To compare the male and female college students on depression level.

- ✓ To study the relationship between suicidal behavior and Depression among male and female college students.

Hypothesis of the Study

- ✓ There will be significant relationship between male and female college students with respect to depression.
- ✓ There will be significant between male and female college students with respect to suicidal behaviour.
- ✓ There will be significant relationship between suicidal behavior and Depression of male and female college students.

Operational definitions

Suicidal Tendency :- Suicidal tendency will be defined as the self-reported presence of suicidal thoughts, plans, intentions, and/or behaviors over the past 12 months as measured by the Suicide Probability. Specific items that will be used to assess suicidal tendency

include: lifetime suicidal ideation and/or suicide attempts, frequency of suicidal ideation over the past years, threat of suicide attempt, and self-reported likelihood of suicidal behaviour in the future.

Suicidal ideation :- *Suicidal ideation, or suicidal thoughts, is the thought process of having ideas, or ruminations about the possibility of completing suicide. It is not a diagnosis but is a symptom of some mental disorders, use of certain psychoactive drugs, and can also occur in response to adverse life events without the presence of a mental disorder.*

Suicidal ideation is associated with depression and other mood disorders; however, many other mental disorders, life events and family events can increase the risk of suicidal ideation. Mental health researchers indicate that healthcare systems should provide treatment for individuals with suicidal ideation, regardless of diagnosis, because of the risk for suicidal acts and repeated problems

associated with suicidal thoughts. There are a number of treatment options for people who experience suicidal ideation.

Suicidal Behaviour :- Suicide is death caused by an act of self-harm that is intended to be lethal. Suicidal behavior includes completed suicide, attempted suicide, and suicidal ideation (thoughts and ideas).

Depression :- Depression will be defined as the presence of at least mild depression symptoms over the past 2 weeks as measured by Beck Depression Inventory tool. Specific depressive symptoms that will be assessed include: depressed mood, anhedonia (diminished interest or pleasure), sleep disturbances, fatigue, appetite changes, changes, low self-esteem, concentration problems, psychomotor retardation/agitation, and suicidal ideation.

Research Method

A descriptive survey design will be adopted for the present study

Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon. It can answer what, where, when and how questions, but not why questions. A descriptive research design can use a wide variety of research methods to investigate one or more variables. Descriptive research does not answer questions about why a certain phenomenon occurs or what the causes are. Answers to such questions are best obtained from randomized and quasi-experimental studies. However, data from descriptive studies can be used to examine the relationships (correlations) among variables. The implication of this is that no variables were manipulated. The study is therefore the ex-post facto type where data is usually collected after the events have already taken place. In this study, the events as mentioned relate to depression and suicidal ideation.

Research Design

A correlational study will be adopted for the present study. A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. A correlation reflects the strength and/or direction of the relationship between two (or more) variables. The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative. Here, The goal of correlational research is to identify variables that have a relationship in which a change in one creates a change in the other—without influence from any extraneous variable. Correlational research is a type of non-experimental research in which two variables are measured and assesses the statistical relationship (i.e., the correlation) between them with little or no effort to control extraneous variables.

Research Variables

Independent Variables

- ✓ Male and female college students
- ✓ Suicidal behaviour

Dependent Variables

- Depression

Population of the Study

The population of the study will be in Lucknow city.

Sample of the Study

The sample will be selected from the 100 college students of age group 18 to 22 years from Lucknow which divided into male and female groups. Purposive Random Sampling Method will be used for present study. The total sample will be 50 males and 50 female college students.

Inclusion & Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion

- Those who in the age group of 18 to 22 years will be included.
- Those who give consent and willing to participate will be included.

Exclusion

- Those who are above 22 years will be excluded.
- Those who are outside the Lucknow will be excluded.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

To begin with the research, first researcher needs to contact the college students who are between 18 to 22 years who are depression and shows suicidal behaviour. The nature of the study was explained to them consent and willing of the college students regarding data collection was taken and they were assured of confidentiality. Researcher needs to pay attention to the type of question and scale of measurement in present study. Since the type of question of

the study was concerned with relationship between the categorical variables, thus there was need for using Correlation Coefficient. The measure of correlation coefficient tend to be close to zero when there is no association and close to the maximum (or maximum) value when there is perfect association.

SPSS software was used for data analyzing in this study.

The test was conducted, score obtained was calculated for each subscale, raw scores was converted into percentile score and then interpretations, conclusions and future suggestions was made on that basis.

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD PROCEDURE

Descriptive statistics was used for data analysis in the proposed study.

Statistics Used: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, was used to get the Correlation coefficients between suicidal tendency and depression.

t-test: The t-test, statistics was evaluated to assess significant difference of Means exists between suicidal behavior variables and suicidal tendency & depression respectively, from the same sample of male and female college students.

Note: 1) Although it's a Correlational Study. It is Important to analyze the impacts Age, gender, violence, abuse, on the suicidal tendency, suicidal behaviour and depression, of the sample, as these Factors play a crucial role.

2) Both person product moment correlation & t-Test, were mentioned in the synopsis.

Tools used for data collection

- *Beck Depression Inventory (1961) by Aaron T. Beck.*
- *Suicide Probability Scale by John G. Cull & Wayne S. Gill.*

Description of tools used

We discuss and understand the tools for data collection of this study.

Beck Depression Inventory

A.T. Beck (1961) developed the BDL, BDI has been used over 40 years to identify and assess depressive symptoms, and has been reported to be highly reliable regardless of the population. It is able to differentiate depressed from non-depressed patients. In addition, BDI is able to assess the severity of depression, and it can diagnose mild, moderate and high levels of depression in depressed people. Vedamurthachar, N., et al.. (2006) and Pilkingtonab. K (2005) used BDI for their studies in India.

Original BDI is a self-administered scale, and it takes approximately 15 minutes to complete, although clients require a fifth fourth grade reading age to adequately understand the questions. The BDT consisted of twenty-one questions about how the subject has been feeling in the last week. Each question has a set of at least four possible answer choices, ranging in intensity. These 21-item scale including mood, pessimism, sense of failure, self-dissatisfaction, guilt, punishment,

self- dislike, self-accusation, suicidal ideas, crying, irritability, social withdrawal, indecisiveness, body image change, work difficulty, insomnia, fatigability. loss of appetite, weight loss, somatic preoccupation, and loss of libido.

It should be mentioned that instrument was used in study (BDI) is a self-reported instrument, and the researcher had no interference in self- observations.

Validity

The average correlation of the BDI total scores with clinical ratings of depression was > 90 for both psychiatric patients and normal adults. The BDI discriminates among subtypes of mood disorders, such as dysthymia and major depression, and symptoms, such as sadness and loss of libido. The BDI also differentiates psychiatric outpatients who are diagnosed with major depression and generalized anxiety disorders.

Reliability

Internal consistency for the BDI ranges from .73 to .92 with a mean of .86 (Beck, Steer, & Garbin, 1988). The BDI demonstrates high internal consistency, with alpha coefficients of .86 and .81 for psychiatric and non-psychiatric populations, respectively (Beck et al., 1988).

Scoring

There is a four-point scale for each item ranging from 0-3. Numerical values of 0, 1, 2 and 3 are assigned to each statement to indicate the degree of severity. The highest possible score from the instrument is 63. A total score of 0-13 is considered minimal depression, 14-19 score mild depression, 20-28 moderate depression, and 29-63 severe depression.

Comments

There are 21 items in the BDI which are seen in the following:

<u>1</u>	Sadness	<u>8</u>	Self Accusation	15	Retardation
<u>2</u>	Permission	<u>9</u>	Suicidal ideation	16	Insomnia
3	Sense of failure	<u>10</u>	Episodes of crying	17	Fatigability
4	Dissatisfaction	<u>11</u>	Irrationality	18	Loss of appetite
5	Guilt	<u>12</u>	Social withdrawal	19	Loss of weight
6	Expectation of punishment	<u>13</u>	Indecisiveness	20	Somatic preoccupation
7	Distike of Self	<u>14</u>	Changes in body image	21	Low level of energy

Suicide Probability Scale

The Suicide Probability Scale (SPS) is a brief, self-report measure designed to aid in the assessment of suicide risk in adolescent and adults. It was developed by John G. Cull & Wayne S. Gill. The SPS is an efficient, cost-effective screening device. It is easy to administer and score, and can be used by trained technicians under the supervision of a qualified professional.

The entire scale can usually be administered, scored, and interpreted in less than 20 minutes, scoring and interpretation can be simplified by using the microcomputer program. The scale may be administered in group setting. The SPS provides four clinical subscales: (1) Hopelessness (12 Items). (2) Suicide Ideation (8 items), (3) Negative Self Evaluation (9 items), and (4) Hostility (7 Items).

Administration and Scoring

Materials needed to administer the hand-scored version of the scale include a pen or pencil and the SPS Rating form. The Rating form has two layers with carbon placed in between. The top layer is intended for the subject. The 36 test items are contained on this sheet along with instructions and spaces for responding to each item. The bottom layer is intended for use by the person administering

the test. In the SPS form use a 6-point rather than an 8-point scale. The SPS is administered individually.

Reliability of the test

The SPS was highly reliable instrument. Alpha and test-retest reliability of .93 compare favorably with similar tests used to assess clinically relevant dimensions, although scores on the subscales produce somewhat smaller correlations.

Statistical Analysis

For the purpose of the present study, Mean, Standard Deviations (SD), t-test, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation will be used. T test will be used to study the significant difference between male and female college students with respect to depression and suicidal behaviour . Further, Pearson Product Moment Correlation will be used to study the relationship between the variable.

The main Ethnical Issues involved in Psychological Research that should be taken care and remembered are as follows:

- **Minimal Risk** : The harm or discomfort should not be more than what is experienced in everyday life by the participants.
- **Confidentiality** : Participants should be protected from social inquiry and their responses should be anonymous and confidential.
- **Informed Consent** : Participants should know about the study, risks involved, protection of their rights, and the rights to withdraw anytime during the conduction of the study.
- **Privacy** : The participants have the right to decide how their information is communicated to others.
- **Deception** : It is involved in studies where some information is withheld or participants are misinformed at any stage of the research.
- **Plagiarism** : This happens when written material from books/articles/journals/internet at any of the research.

Chapter 5 : RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In this chapter, results of the study are presented. In the first section, the results of the *Descriptive statistics* including means and standard deviations regarding to depression and of the sample are presented. The results of *t-test* and *Pearson Product Moment Correlation* which was performed to examine the difference between male and female college students with respect to depression and suicidal behaviour. Participants regarding to their depression and suicidal behaviour will be introduced. The Determination of the difference between females and males regarding to depression and suicidal behaviour are also covered in the second part.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

TABLE 1 :- showed the Demographic information of respondents in the present study. There were ___ (n=) college students were involved in this study. The respondents were divided protionately according to the number of students of students, with 50% male (n=50) and 50% females (n=50) students.

TABLE 1 :-**CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PARTICIPANTS**

<u>CHARACTERISTICS</u>	<u>N</u>	<u>(%)</u>
<u>Gender</u>		
Female	50	50.00
Male	50	50.00
<u>Age of respondents</u>		
<u>18 - 21</u>	100	100.00

HYPOTHESIS 1 : THERE WILL BE SIGNIFICANT BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO DEPRESSION

Correlation analysis is used to find out the relationship between two variables. The correlation co efficient is valued in the field of education as the measure of relationship between test scores and other measures of performance. In the present study, the correlation analysis is used to find out the relationship between Suicidal Tendency and Depression.

TABLE 2 :-**CORRELATIONS BETWEEN SUICIDAL TENDENCY AND DEPRESSION**

	<u>SUICIDAL TENDENCY</u>	<u>DEPRESSION</u>
<u>SUICIDAL TENDENCY</u>	1.00	
<u>DEPRESSION</u>	0.131	1.00

****p < 0.01**

The above table shows that there is a significant positive relationship of Suicidal Tendency with depression among college students; represent that higher level of suicidality increase Suicidal Tendency. Similarly, a significant positive correlation was found between suicidal tendency and depression; higher depression increase suicidal behaviour among college students. Thus, there is a positive relationship between suicidal tendency and depression which is significant at 0.001 level of significance. The correlation values between suicidal tendency and depression is 0.600. Similarly, positive relationship found between depression and suicidal

tendency. The correlation value is 0.328 which is significance at 0.001 level of significance.

Thus, Hypothesis 1 stated that there is a relationship between Suicidal Tendency and Depression among college students is accepted.

TABLE 3 :-

CORRELATION BETWEEN SUICIDAL TENDENCY AND DEPRESSION (FEMALE)

	SUICIDAL TENDENCY	DEPRESSION
SUICIDAL TENDENCY	1.00	
DEPRESSION	0.175	1.00

** $p < 0.01$

This table depict a significant negative relationship of Suicidal Tendency with depression and suicidal behaviour among college students , significant at 0.01 level; there is an increased risk of suicidal tendency with decreasing level of depression among college students. Similarly, depression found dependent on suicidal tendency among female college

students, decrease level of depression increase the risk of Suicidal ideation among female college students.

TABLE 4 :-

CORRELATION BETWEEN SUICIDAL TENDENCY AND DEPRESSION (MALE)

	<u>SUICIDAL TENDENCY</u>	<u>DEPRESSION</u>
<u>SUICIDAL TENDENCY</u>	<u>1.00</u>	
<u>DEPRESSION</u>	<u>0.107</u>	<u>1.00</u>

** $p < 0.01$

This shows that male college students demonstrate a significant negative correlation between suicidal tendency and depression; represent that higher suicidal behaviour reduce the chances of developing manifestation of suicidal tendency and subsequently development of depression and suicide in students. Although a negative insignificant relationship was observed between depression and suicidal behaviour in male college students.

HYPOTHESIS 2 : THERE WILL BE SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE COLLEGE STUDENTS RESPECT TO SUICIDAL BEHAVIOUR.

This analysis provides inference involving determination of statistical significance of difference between categories with reference to the selected variables. In the present investigation the investigator applied *t*-test.

TABLE 5 :-

SHOWING THE MEAN COMPARISON OF STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO THEIR DEPRESSION LEVEL .

	<u>N</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>	<u>t-value</u>	<u>P-value</u>
<i>Suicidal Tendency</i>	50	15.02	1.86	5.8269	0.001
<i>Depression</i>	50	16.89	1.30		

It can be concluded from table 4 there is significant difference in depression among students with respect to their depression levels.

HYPOTHESIS 3 : THERE WILL BE SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SUICIDAL BEHAVIOR AND DEPRESSION OF MALE AND FEMALE COLLEGE STUDENTS.

TABLE 6 :-

SHOWING THE MEAN COMPARISON OF SUICIDAL BEHAVIOUR AND DEPRESSION AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS.

	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>T-value</i>	<i>P-value</i>
<i>Suicidal Tendency</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>54.55</i>	<i>2.55</i>	<i>2.179*</i>	<i>0.0317</i>
<i>Depression</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>55.58</i>	<i>2.16</i>		

Sample size = 100 = With help of both variables (Independent & Dependent), suicidal tendency and depression are represented. Suicidal behaviour = suicidal behaviour symptoms = Depression = Depression symptoms = Beck Depression Inventory = Beck Depression Inventory Questionnaire = Suicidal Probability Scale = Suicidal Probability Scale Questionnaire. Df = 98, *significant at 0.05 **significant at 0.01

Chapter 6 : CONCLUSION

The goal that was set out focus on qualitative findings in order to gain in depth understanding of factors leading to suicidal behaviour among male and female college students. To compare the male and female college students on depression level and to study the relationship between suicidal behavior and Depression among male and female college students.

On the basis of analysis, interpretation and discussion of the results presented in the foregoing chapters, conclusions have been drawn which are reported below :-

- There is a relationship between suicidal tendency and depression among male and female college students.*
- There is significant difference in suicidal behavior among male and female with respect to depression ($t=5.8269$). This shows that students feels more depression in college, (mean=16.89) as compared to students*

who shows suicidal behaviour (mean=15.02). The reason could be that students who shows suicidal behaviour was due to depression.

- There is significant difference between suicidal tendency among female and male college students. The students who were depressed scored low suicidal tendency than the students who were depressed shows suicidal behaviour.

Conclusions

The study findings suggest that suicidal tendency and suicidal behaviour are dependent on each other in male and female college students. Severity of suicidal tendency is found associated with suicidal behaviour among male and female college students; however, this is missing in male college students with respect to depression.

The college students who shows suicidal behaviour are more vulnerable and depression usually found in those with suicidal ideations and suicide attempts. Depression is attached with anxiety, high levels of

stress, and in the worst possible case with suicide. It can also affect one's life, social life and relationship with others. This can further lead to isolation from them and society that may create other issues.

Implication

The present research investigation has facilitated in identifying different problem faced by the college students. This proposes for further research in this related direction. The study emphasized upon the health care providers, educators, mental health professional and policy makers to better understand the need of training in identifying and counselling the students to prevent suicide among college students.

The study lays down the message that psychologist and mental health professional should make an extra effort to develop some training programs that helps students to gain in depth understanding of the factors leading to suicidal attempt among college students. There us increased rate of suicide in India and along with other age group it is increased in students also.

Delimitation

- ❖ This study was delimited to only college students in Lucknow.
- ❖ The study was further delimited to 50 males and 50 female college students.
- ❖ This study delimited to college students who were 18 to 21 years, below 18 and above 22 years were excluded.

Chapter 7 : Suggestions for further research

Future scope of this dissertation has opened multiple avenues for further study and research . Improvement can be further accelerated by adopting a zero suicide ambition that helps health care professional reach a tipping point in its mindset, from resigned acceptance of suicide to active prevention of suicide. Therefore, the future researchers should take a large sample outside the Lucknow in order to increase the generalization of the results. Other variables should be taken in consideration. Since, this investigation is restricted to college students therefore the findings cannot be generalized to other age group students. The other demographic variables such as etc. have not been studied which might play an important role in analyzing other mental health problem and behaviour, Understand that people who were depressed are prone to suicidal ideation, when someone who is experiencing family issues, violence, abuse, harassment, stress, anxiety, isolate themselves and behaviour problem.

Further research in the area is very much required to widen the findings and awareness of the issue of this present study. This present investigation studied the college students who are between 18 – 21 age group, similar study can conducted in future but with different age groups.

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QUESTIONNAIRE

APPENDIX – A

Beck's Depression Inventory

This Questionnaire consists of 21 groups of statements. After reading each group of statements carefully, choose one statement in each group which best describes the way you have feeling the past week, including today. If several statements within a group seem to apply equally well, circle each one. Be sure to read all the statements in each group before making your choice.

.....

General information

Sex :

Marital Status :

Age :

Degree of Education :

.....

I Answer :

- 0. I do not feel sad.*
- 1. I feel sad.*
- 2. I am sad all the time and I can not snap out of it.*
- 3. I am so sad and unhappy that I can not stand it.*

II Answer :

- 0. I am not particularly discouraged about the future.*
- 1. I fell discouraged about the future.*
- 2. I fell I have nothing to look forward to.*
- 3. I feel the future is hopeless and that things cannot improve.*

III Answer :

- 0. I do not feel like a failure.*
- 1. I feel I have failed more than the average person.*
- 2. As I look back on my life, all I can see is a lot of failures.*
- 3. I feel I a complete failure as a person.*

IV Answer :

- 0. I get as much satisfaction out of things as I need to.*
- 1. I do not enjoy things the way I used to.*

2. *I do not get real satisfaction out of anything anymore.*
3. *I am dissatisfied or bored with everything.*

V Answer :

0. *I do not feel particularly guilty.*
1. *I feel guilty a good part of the time.*
2. *I feel quite guilty most of the time.*
3. *I feel guilty all of the time.*

VI Answer :

0. *I do not feel I am being punished.*
1. *I feel I may be punished.*
2. *I expect to be punished.*
3. *I feel I am being punished.*

VII Answer :

0. *I do not feel disappointed in myself.*
1. *I am disappointed in myself.*
2. *I am disgusted with myself.*
3. *I hate myself.*

VII Answer :

- 0. I do not feel I am any worse than anybody else.*
- 1. I am critical of myself for my weakness or mistakes.*
- 2. I blame myself all the time for my faults.*
- 3. I blame myself for everything bad that happens.*

IX Answer :

- 0. I do not have any thoughts of killing myself.*
- 1. I have thoughts of killing myself, but I would not carry them out.*
- 2. I would like to kill myself.*
- 3. I would kill myself if I had the chance.*

X Answer :

- 0. I do not cry any more than usual.*
- 1. I cry more than I used to.*
- 2. I cry all the time now.*
- 3. I used to be able to cry, but now I can not cry even though I want to.*

XI Answer :

- 0. I am no more irritated by things than I ever was.*

1. *I am slightly more irritated now than usual.*
2. *I am quite annoyed or irritated a good deal of the time.*
3. *I feel irritated all the time.*

XII Answer :

0. *I have not lost interest in other people.*
1. *I am less interested in other people than I used to be.*
2. *I have lost most of my interest in other people.*
3. *I have lost all of my interest in other people.*

XIII Answer :

0. *I made decisions about as well as I ever could.*
1. *I put off making decisions more than I used to.*
2. *I have greater difficultly in making decisions more than I used to.*
3. *I can not make decisions at all anymore.*

XIV Answer :

0. *I do not feel that I look any worse than I used to.*
1. *I am worried that I am looking old or unattractive.*

2. *I feel that there are permanent changes in my appearance that make me look unattractive.*
3. *I believe that I look ugly.*

XV Answer :

0. *I can work about as well as before.*
1. *It takes an extra effort to get started at doing something.*
2. *I have to push myself very hard to do anything.*
3. *I can not do any work at all.*

XVI Answer :

0. *I can sleep as well as usual.*
1. *I do not sleep as well as I used to.*
2. *I wake up 1-2 hours earlier than usual and find it hard to get back to sleep.*
3. *I wake up several hours earlier than I used to and cannot get back to sleep.*

XVII Answer :

0. *I do not get more tired than usual.*
1. *I get tired more easily than I used to.*

2. *I get tired from doing almost anything.*

3. *I am too tired to do anything.*

XVIII Answer :

0. *My appetite is no worse than usual.*

1. *My appetite is not as good as it used to be.*

2. *My appetite is much worse now.*

3. *I have no appetite at all anymore.*

XIX Answer :

0. *I have not lost much weight, if any, lately.*

1. *I have lost more than five pounds (2.267 kg).*

2. *I have lost more than ten pounds (4.535 kg).*

3. *I have lost more than fifteen pounds (6.803kg).*

I am porously trying to lose weight by eating less.

XX Answer :

0. *I am no more worried about my health than usual.*

1. *I am worried about physical problem such as aches and pains, or upset stomach, or constipation.*

2. *I am very worried about physical problem and it is hard to think of much else.*
3. *I am so worried about my physical problem that I cannot think about anything else.*

XXI Answer :

0. *I have not noticed any recent change in my interest in sex.*
1. *I am less interested in sex than I used to be.*
2. *I am much less interested in sex now.*
3. *I have lost interest in sex completely.*

QUESTIONNAIRE

APPENDIX-B

Suicide Probability Scale

Instructions - This 36-item self-report measure was designed to help assess suicide risk in adolescents and adults ages 14 and older and takes 5-10 minutes to complete. Respondents indicate how often each statement applies to him or her, using a 4-point scale. The SPS provides scores for four clinical scales: Hopelessness, Suicide Ideation, Negative Self-Evaluation, and Hostility. Cronbach's alpha for the SPS was .92 in a sample of psychiatric inpatients (Bisconer and Gross, 2007). The same study reported a correlation coefficient of .82 between the SPS and the Beck Depression Inventory.

<i>S.no.</i>	<i>Cues</i>	<i>Never</i>	<i>Sometime</i>	<i>Rarely</i>	<i>Often</i>
1	<i>Hopelessness</i>				
1.	<i>Have you ever felt depressed and thought of committing suicide when you scored low marks?</i>				
2.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide when you are not able to write your exam properly even though there was enough time?</i>				

3.	<i>Have you ever thought of self-injury when you are not able to score high marks because of selecting subject that you disliked?</i>				
4.	<i>Have you ever got depressed when your parents advised for scoring low marks in exams?</i>				
5.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide about your problems in learning?</i>				
6.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide when you advised for your mistakes?</i>				
7.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide when you got depressed after comparing your marks with friends?</i>				
8.	<i>Have you ever got depressed about your disability in understanding subjects?</i>				
9.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide when you could not continue your studies because of family circumstances?</i>				
10.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide when you could not continue your studies because of family circumstances?</i>				
11.	<i>Have you ever got depressed because of the distractions in education caused by others?</i>				
12.	<i>Have you ever got depressed when you are affected by sexual harassment?</i>				
11	<i>Suicide Ideation</i>				
13.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide of your parent's remarriage?</i>				
14.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide because of your parents' divorce?</i>				

15.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide due to caste discrimination?</i>				
16.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide because of religious discrimination?</i>				
17.	<i>Have you ever got depressed as you don't have anyone to guide in the society?</i>				
18.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide when you got depressed when the society strongly condemns your fault?</i>				
19.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide when the society strongly condemned for the fault you haven't committed?</i>				
20.	<i>Have you ever got depressed when you were denied opportunities by the society?</i>				
III	<i>Negative Self-Self-Evaluation</i>				
21.	<i>Have you ever thought of your future aims and felt depressed?</i>				
22.	<i>Have you ever got depressed when you feel that you have poor administration skills?</i>				
23.	<i>Have you ever thought of self-injury because of the death of your loved ones?</i>				
24.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide because of not having good relationship with friends?</i>				
25.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide whenever you lose your self-respect among friends?</i>				
26.	<i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide about getting punishment before others for a small mistake committed earlier?</i>				

<p>27.</p> <p>28.</p> <p>29.</p>	<p><i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide because of love failure?</i></p> <p><i>Have you ever got depressed when you felt alone losing parents and relations?</i></p> <p><i>Have you ever got depressed when you are ignored based on your complexion?</i></p>				
<p>IV</p> <p>30.</p> <p>31.</p> <p>32.</p> <p>33.</p> <p>34.</p> <p>35.</p> <p>36.</p>	<p><i>Hostility</i></p> <p><i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide when you were not able to Fulfill your desire due to economic status?</i></p> <p><i>Have you ever got depressed because of the economic status of your parents?</i></p> <p><i>Have you ever got depressed because you don't have basic facility in your house for studying?</i></p> <p><i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide because you were not able to reach your goal due to economic status?</i></p> <p><i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide when you could not fulfill your necessities because of a large family?</i></p> <p><i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide when you felt that your parents did not occupy a high socio economic status?</i></p> <p><i>Have you ever thought of committing suicide because you are unable to continue your higher education due to economic status?</i></p>				